

Academic Writing and Its Impediments among Academicians in a Southern Nigerian State

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Suggested Citation

Ijah, R.F.O.A., Eli, S.F., Akoko, S., Babatunde, S., & Mato, C.N. (2025). Academic Writing and Its Impediments among Academicians in a Southern Nigerian State. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(1), 338-352. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(1\).30](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(1).30)

Abstract:

Background: The university is an academic community of diverse disciplines saddled with the responsibility of ensuring transfer of knowledge to the younger generation in a structured manner. The aim of this study was to evaluate academic writings and the associated impediments among academicians in Port Harcourt, Nigeria over a period of three years. **Materials and Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out in educational institutions of higher learning in Port Harcourt, Nigeria from November 2021 to April 2022. A total of 438 academic staff were recruited using self-administered questionnaire and a multi-stage

sampling technique. Collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel® and analyzed with SPSS version 25 to compute summary statistics. Chi-square test was used to test differences in proportions, and to test association between variables, at a significant level of 5%. **Results:** The mean age of respondents was 43.5 years (95% CI = 42.69 or 44.27), while the male: female ratio was 2:1. Twenty-nine (5.8%) reported having published 50 or more academic papers. The majority (n = 181, 36.1%) reported the frequency of publication as 2-4 publications per year. Lack of funds for research (n=346, 69.1%), lack of time for research (n = 230, 52.5%), societal distractions (n = 105, 24.0%), poor knowledge of reference management software (n = 102, 20.4%), were the most common impediments. **Conclusion:** This study shows that challenges still exist among academicians from idea conceptualization to journal publication. Intensifying the drive for academic workshop in manuscript writing and reference management software is highly recommended.

Introduction

The university is an academic community of different and diverse disciplines saddled with the responsibility of ensuring transfer of knowledge to the younger generation in a structured manner, conduct of research, and also serves as a pool of reformed minds for service to the society. Central to achieving these goals is writing, a component of the four skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) desirable for effective communication in any language (Ariana, 2010). The art of learning, comprehension, application and synthesis of new knowledge is a skill resident in the cognitive domain, and well describes effective academic writing that involves creative reflection, documentation of issues logically in formal written format for solving problems in society (Defazio et al., 2010). From conceptualization of an idea of what to write (or research on) to conclusion and references are tasks that are learned. To students, teachers, and researchers alike, writing is a subject of interest, being a central pillar of language learning (Ariana, 2010). Writing to learn and learning to write is a subject of considerable emphasis, although very few give the needed attention to writing (Gilbert & Graham, 2010; Magrath et al., 2003; Wyse, 2003). It had been posited that although the transition from a novice to a master in writing is poorly understood, that it is associated with changes in the writer and his / her environment (Graham, 2006; Graham et al., 2013). However, essential components of academic writing skills have been reported to be proficiency in language abilities beyond conversational fluency and preparatory work (Hinkel, 2013). Furthermore, giving and receiving criticisms has been described as part of good scholarly writing, though not to a paralyzing degree (Brownson & Jones, 2009; Caffarella & Barnett, 2000).

Writing is an art that is applicable to all disciplines with its unique styles or pattern. The style, attitude, cohesion, and tone in writing are also known to showcase a lot about the writer (Hyland, 2002). Writing has different uses: for

teaching and learning (Ackerman, 1993; Gere, 1985; Parker & Goodkin, 1987; Selfe & Arbabi, 1983); expressing opinion, to document facts for the future, for research, promote a business (Ranaut, 2018), psychologic and physiologic benefit (when one writes about one's feelings and experiences) (Smyth, 1998), powerful tool for influencing others (Graham et al., 2013), for keeping in contact with family friends / colleagues (Graham et al., 2013), for employment or promotion (Ariana, 2010), projects professional image (Ariana, 2010), etc. However, to the academician the use of writing for teaching, learning and research are foremost. The value placed by an individual or society on these reasons for writing, amidst competing interests, directly or indirectly serves as incentives that motivate for involvement in academic writing (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002; Forte & Bruckman, 2005; McClelland, 1985). The much needed benefit of academic writing / research is fully manifest when there is a handshake between "the gown and the town", i.e. translating the writings / research into development (Goldstein, 2009).

Academic writing was emphasized for students in the areas of sciences, technology and commercials, in the National Policy on Education (2013) for its multifactorial roles of enabling advanced ideas through creativity, critical thinking and presentation of sound arguments (Anukaenyi & Ozomadu, 2019; Ezeh-Origie). Earlier publications on research and publications in Nigeria had thrown open different layers of issues from lack of sponsorship, through lack of reward, to lack of application of research findings (Abdulmumini; Egwunyenga, 2008; Ibegbulam & Jacintha, 2016; Igbojekwe et al., 2015; Ochai & Nwafor, 1990). Challenges associated with writing have also been identified as an impediment to education and development in Nigeria beyond 2020 (Ezeh-Origie). As it is the practice around the world, the number of publications / research possessed by a lecturer is the main criterion among others for the appraisal for promotion to higher ranks

in Nigerian universities. This is what spurred on the popular phrase “publish or perish!” within the academia. The criteria for assessment and number of published works may differ from one university to the other, but without publications, no lecturer in a Nigerian university can be promoted from one rank to the other; yet some lecturers do not conduct research or studies for publication. What could be the constraints to academic writing for these lecturers? What are the common areas of difficulties in conducting a research work from idea conceptualization to publication of an article, as it affects lecturers? The aim of this study therefore was to evaluate academic writings and its associated impediments among academicians in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

It was a descriptive cross-sectional study carried out from November 2021 to April 2022.

Study Area

The city of Port Harcourt is host to two large federal government institutions – the University of Port Harcourt and the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital; four Rivers State Government tertiary institutions – the Rivers State University, Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, Ignatius Ajuru University, the Elechi Amadi Polytechnic; the College of Health Technology & Nursing; and a private university – the PAMO University of Medical Sciences. The study was carried out among teaching staff of these educational facilities in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Study Population

Lecturers of tertiary educational institutions in Port Harcourt were recruited.

Sample Size Determination

The minimum sample size of approximately 400 was determined using the Cochran formula:

$$n_0 = \frac{z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1-p)}{e^2} \quad (1)$$

where e : desired level of precision, the margin of error; p : the fraction of the population (as percentage) that displays the attribute; z : the z -value, extracted from a z -table.

Study Instrument

Semi-structured, self-administered questionnaires.

Sampling Method

The multi-stage sampling method was used to distribute 525 questionnaires to lecturers in the study, and 438 questionnaires were retrieved. The institutions were identified and specific quota was allocated to each university/institution (stratified sampling method). In each institution a list of departments was made out of which some were selected through systematic sampling method. Specific quota was allocated to the selected departments for administration. The convenience sampling method was then used to administer the questionnaires to every reachable lecturer in the departments who gave consent for inclusion in the study, evaluating issues on academic writing over a period of three years (2019-2021).

Study Variables

Socio-demographic characteristics, papers published, publication types collaboration, use of writing aids, areas of challenges in academic writing, and impediment to academic writing.

Data Analysis

Data obtained was formed into tables and analyzed using the IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0 (or 26.0). Chi square test was used for statistical significance and logistic regression (odd ratio) for association between variables.

Bias

The quota for the University of Port Harcourt / Teaching Hospital could not be reached despite several efforts at the time of the study.

Validity / Reliability of Instrument

The study data scrutinized by all the authors for authenticity or otherwise before use. The

Cronbach alpha (in SPSS) was used to test the reliability of the study instrument (0.730).

Results

Out of 525 semi-structured questionnaires that were distributed, 438 were completed and retrieved giving a response rate of 83.4%.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Frequency (n = 438)	Percentage
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	294	67.1
Female	144	32.9
<i>Age (Mean= 43.48±8.39, 95%CI: 42.69 – 44.27)</i>		
20 - 24 years	2	.5
25 - 29 years	9	2.1
30 - 34 years	58	13.2
35 - 39 years	68	15.5
40 - 44 years	121	27.6
45 - 49 years	78	17.8
50 - 54 years	49	11.2
55 - 59 years	42	9.6
60 - 64 years	8	1.8
65 years and above	3	.7
<i>Marital Status</i>		
Single	84	19.2
Married	349	79.7
Separated	5	1.1
<i>Religion</i>		
Christianity	372	84.9
Islam	6	1.4
Traditional	14	3.2
No response	46	10.5
<i>Academic Rank</i>		
Assistant Lecturer	115	26.3
Lecturer II	86	19.8
Lecturer I	77	17.6
Senior Lecturer	94	21.5
Associate Professor	41	9.4
Professor	25	5.7
<i>Institution of training or service</i>		
University of Port Harcourt (UPH)	171	39.0
Rivers State University	212	48.4
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education	39	8.9
Elechi Amadi Polytechnic	1	0.2
PAMO University of Medical Sciences (PUMS)	15	3.4

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 1. There were 294 (67.1%) male respondents, and 144 (32.9%) females. The mean age was 43.48±8.39 (95% CI: 42.69 – 44.27), and majority (n = 325,

74.2%) were between 30 and 49 years of age. Three hundred and forty-nine (79.7%) were married. There were 115 (26.3%) assistant lecturers, 86 (19.8%) lecturer II, 77 (17.6%)

lecturer I, 94 (21.5%) senior lecturers, 41 (9.4%) associate professors, and 25 (5.7%) professors.

Table 2. Papers Published, Collaboration, Writing Aids, "Late Hunting" for Papers for Promotion

Variables	Frequency (n =438)	Percentage
<i>Ever published a paper in a journal</i>		
Yes	416	95.0
No	22	5.0
<i>Number of papers ever published</i>		
None	22	5.0
Less than 10	70	16.0
10 - 19	117	26.7
20 - 29	101	23.1
30 - 39	64	14.6
40 - 49	35	8.0
50 and above	29	6.6
<i>Average paper published per year</i>		
None	22	5.0
Less than 2	49	11.2
2 - 4	161	36.8
5 - 7	132	30.1
8 - 10	40	9.1
more than 10	34	7.8
<i>Do you Collaborate with other colleagues for publication</i>		
Yes	425	97.0
No	13	3.0
<i>Proficient in the use of computer (MS word/Excel etc.)</i>		
Yes	429	97.9
No	3	0.7
Not sure	6	1.4
<i>Ever "late hunting" for papers for promotion</i>		
Yes	107	24.4
No	209	47.7
Not sure	122	27.9
<i>Ever use any Aids in publications</i>		
Yes	421	96.1
No	7	1.6
Not sure	10	2.3

Table 2 highlights respondents' academic paper publications, involvement in collaboration, use of writing aids, and the phenomenon of "late-hunting" for papers for promotion. Four hundred and sixteen (95%) respondents had published academic papers in journals before, while 22 (5%) had never published. Twenty-nine (6.6%) respondents reported having published 50 or more academic papers. Among those who had more papers, 117 (26.7%) respondents had 10-19 publications, and 101 (23.1%) had a total

of 20-29 publications. The average number of papers published per year by the larger number of respondents were 2-4 (n = 161, 36.8%), and 5-7 (n = 132, 30.1%). Only 34 (7.8%) of the respondents had more than 10 academic papers published per year. Although respondents collaborated (n = 425, 97.0%), asserted to being proficient in the use of computer (n = 429, 97.9%), and used some aids to academic publications (n = 421, 96.1%), 107 (24.4%) were still involved in "late-hunting" for papers for

promotion, and others were unwilling (not sure) to admit so (n = 122, 27.9%).

Table 3. Academic Publication Types (n = 438)

	Yes		No	
<i>Study designs commonly published</i>				
Descriptive Studies	390	89.0	48	11.0
Analytical Studies	297	67.8	141	32.2
Experimental Studies	333	76.0	105	24.0
Dissertation	246	56.2	192	43.8
<i>Category of Publication commonly published</i>				
Original article	377	86.1	61	13.9
Case Report	150	34.2	288	65.8
Case Series	78	17.8	360	82.2
Review Articles	163	37.2	275	62.8
Systematic Review	82	18.7	356	81.3
Letter to the Editor	58	13.2	380	86.8
Editorials	81	18.5	357	81.5
Conference abstract	106	24.2	332	75.8
Monographs	106	24.2	332	75.8
Essays	62	14.2	376	85.8
Commentary writings	49	11.2	389	88.8
Technical reports	55	12.6	383	87.4
Theses and Dissertations	260	59.4	178	40.6

Table 3 shows the respondents' academic publication types. Responses on multiple options on study designs commonly published shows that more than 50.0% had published descriptive / observational studies, analytical

studies, experimental studies and dissertation. The category of publication cuts across original article, case report, case series, review articles, systematic review, commentary writings, theses & dissertations, etc.

Table 4. Use of Specific Aids, Areas of Challenges, and Impediment to Academic Writing (n = 438)

	Yes (%)		No (%)	
<i>Aids to improve skills in publications used</i>				
Research guide	308	70.3	130	29.7
Audio-Visual Research Aids	210	47.9	228	52.1
Research Fair	163	37.2	275	62.8
Reading Journal Articles	231	52.7	207	47.3
Academic Conferences	145	33.1	293	66.9
Grants	191	43.6	247	56.4
Good knowledge of computer use	120	27.4	318	72.6
<i>Challenging section / areas in academic writing</i>				
Conceptualization of research idea	121	27.6	317	72.4
Organizational Problems	49	11.2	389	88.8
Literature Search	85	19.4	353	80.6
Methodology Problem	71	16.2	367	83.8
Language inefficiency	7	1.6	431	98.4
Evaluation Issues	56	12.8	382	87.2
The art of writing and citing	42	9.6	396	90.4
Referencing	94	21.5	344	78.5

Lack of time for research	220	50.2	218	49.8
<i>Opinion on impediments to academic writing</i>				
Lack of funds for research	305	69.6	133	30.4
Societal distractions	105	24.0	333	76.0
Not attending Seminars/Courses on academic	35	8.0	403	92.0
Poor computer knowledge	20	4.6	418	95.4
Poor knowledge of reference management software (Endnote, Mendeley)	81	18.5	357	81.5
Lack of Collaboration	48	11.0	390	89.0
Poor English usage	11	2.5	427	97.5
Lack of interest in writing	23	5.3	415	94.7
Lack of time for research	230	52.5	208	47.5

Table 4 shows use of specific aids to academic writing, and highlights some sections / areas of challenges in academic writing in the 21st century. Respondents' known aids to improve skills in publications included: reading journal articles (n = 231, 52.7%), use of research guide (n = 308, 70.3%), having good knowledge of computer (n = 120, 27.4%), attending academic conferences (n = 145, 33.1%), audio-visual research aids (n = 210, 47.9%), attending research fair (n = 163, 37.2%), and grants (n = 191, 43.6%). Challenging sections / areas in academic writing were asserted by respondents in decreasing order of responses were: lack of

time for research (n = 220, 50.2%), conceptualization of research idea (n = 121, 27.6%), referencing (n = 94, 21.5%), literature search (n = 85, 19.4%), problems with methodology (n = 71, 16.2%), evaluation issues (n = 56, 12.8%), organizational problems (n = 49, 11.2%), the art of writing and citing (n = 42, 9.6%), and language insufficiency (n = 7, 1.6%). Lack of funds for research (n = 305, 69.9%), lack of time for research (n = 230, 52.5%), societal distractions (n = 105, 24.0%), poor knowledge of reference management software like Endnote, Mendeley (n = 81, 18.5%), were the most asserted impediments.

Table 5. Relationship between Ever Published a Paper in a Journal and Ever Involved in a Collaboration with Others (n = 438)

<i>Ever involved in a collaboration with others</i>	Ever published a paper in a journal			(X ²)	P-Value
	Yes	No	Total		
Yes	410 (96.5%)	15 (3.5%)	425		
No	6 (46.2%)	7 (53.8%)	13	66.945	0.000
Not Sure	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0		
Total	416	22	438		

Table 5 shows relationship between “ever published a paper in a journal” and “ever

involved in a collaboration with others”. This was found to be statistically significant (p <000).

Table 6. Relationship between “Ever Published a Paper in a Journal” and Selected Demographic Profile (n = 438)

		Ever published a paper in a journal			(X ²)	P-Value
		Yes	No	Total		
Sex	Male	280 (95.2%)	14 (4.8%)	294		
	Female	136 (94.4%)	8 (5.6%)	144	0.128	0.441
Age	20 - 24 years	1 (50.0%)	1 (50.0%)	2		

	25 - 29 years	6 (66.7%)	3 (33.3%)	9		
	30 - 34 years	53 (91.4%)	5 (8.6%)	58		
	35 - 39 years	65 (95.6%)	3 (4.4%)	68	28.285	0.001
	40 - 44 years	117 (96.7%)	4 (3.3%)	121		
	45 - 49 years	76 (97.4%)	2 (2.6)	78		
	50 - 54 years	46 (93.9%)	3 (6.1%)	49		
	55 - 59 years	41 (97.6%)	1 (2.4%)	42		
	60 - 64 years	8 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	8		
	> 64 years	3 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2		
Marital Status	Single	76 (90.5%)	8 (9.5%)	84		
	Married	335 (96.0%)	14 (4.0%)	349	4.580	0.101
	Separated/ Divorced	5 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5		
Rank	Postgraduate Students (Masters)	0 (0.0%)	4 (100.0%)	4		
	Postgraduate Students (PhD)	1(50.0%)	1 (50.0%)	2	112.713	0.000
	Assistant Lecturer	100 (87.0%)	15 (13.0%)	115		
	Lecturer II	81 (98.8%)	1 (1.2%)	82		
	Lecturer I	74 (98.7%)	1 (1.3%)	75		
	Senior Lecturer	94 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	94		
	Associate Professor	41 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	41		
	Professor	25 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	209		
	Total	416	22	438		

Table 6 shows the relationship between “ever published a paper in a journal” and selected demographic profile. The relationship between sex and “ever published a paper in a journal were” was not statistically significant ($p=0.441$). Proportion of those ever published a paper in a journal significantly increased among those aged 30-34 years and reach the peak among those 64 years and above. Hence, age of academicians can

be a factor in publishing in a journal as the relationship was statistically significant ($p = 0.001$). The relationship between lecturers’ academic rank and “ever published a paper in a journal” was statistically significant ($p= 0.000$), However, the relationship between marital status and “ever published a paper in a journal” showed no statistically significant difference ($p= 0.101$).

Table 7. Relationship between Ever Published a Paper in a Journal and Impediment to Academic Writing

		Ever published a paper in a journal			(X ²)	P-Value
		Yes	No	Total		
Lack of funds for research	Yes	289 (94.8%)	16 (305%)	305	0.105	0.477
	No	127 (95.5%)	6 (4.5%)	133		
Societal distractions	Yes	96 (91.4%)	9 (8.6%)	105	3.646	0.054
	No	320 (96.1%)	13 (3.9%)	333		
Not attending Seminars	Yes	34 (97.1%)	1 (2.9%)	35	0/374	0.460
	No	382 (94.8%)	21 (5.2%)	403		
Poor computer knowledge	Yes	17 (85.0%)	3 (15.0%)	20	4.373	0.072
	No	399 (95.5%)	19 (4.5%)	418		
Poor knowledge of referencing management software	Yes	77 (95.1%)	4 (4.9%)	81	0.969	0.615
	No	339 (95.0%)	18 (5.0%)	357		
Poor English usage	Yes	9 (81.8%)	2 (18.2%)	11	4.096	0.101
	No	407 (95.3%)	20 (4.7%)	427		
Lack of interest in writing	Yes	22 (95.7%)	1 (4.3%)	23	0.023	0.676

	No	394 (94.9%)	21 (5.1%)	415		
Lack of time for research	Yes	215 (93.5%)	15 (6.5%)	230	2.281	0.097
	No	201 (96.6%)	7 (3.4%)	208		
	Total	467	145	612		

Table 7 shows the relationship between ever published a paper in a journal and impediment to academic writing. The relationship between “ever published a paper in a journal” and lack of funds for research, societal distraction, not attending seminars, poor computer knowledge, poor knowledge of reference management software (Endnote, Mendeley), respectively were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, poor English usage ($p = 0.441$), lack of interest in writing ($p = 0.676$), and lack of time for research ($p = 0.097$) were not statistically related to ever published a paper in a journal and hence does not appear to be impediments to academic writing among the studied respondents.

Discussion

The ability to read and write is one of the attributes that shapes a society’s level of development. There is little wonder then when the men and women of the gown are expected to write, and impart similar writing skills to the next generation in the society. A handshake of the gown with the town is therefore often craved for in most societies (Brockliss, 2000; Chaddock, 2012; Mosier, 2015; Oladele, 2013). Our study evaluated academic writing and its impediments among members of the gown, and males, Christians, and the married dominated the demographic characteristics. This information is not unusual as the study was conducted in the Christian dominated Southern Nigerian State (Christian & Sunday, 2013; Salawu, 2010), and expectedly most respondents being within 35-49 years range, were married. The junior and middle-class lecturers were in the majority, with few Professors and Associate Professors. Almost half of the respondents were from the Rivers State University (RSU), and above a third from the University of Port Harcourt (UPH). This finding does not in any way suggest that there were more lecturers in RSU than UPH, as the latter is a bigger federal institution that has

long been in existence, and probably also contributed to training those in the RSU. The timing of data collection for this study may have significantly contributed to this picture. More than half of the respondents had publications across different study designs, and majority were descriptive / observational studies. Publication type were mostly original articles.

Global visibility and competitiveness is a subject of concern to many higher educational institutions (Chou & Chan, 2016), and most governments adopt measures and programs to enhance the research output of their academicians (Chou & Chan, 2016; Chou & Ching, 2012; Ishikawa, 2014; Suh & Park, 2014; Yang & Welch, 2012). Critical in evaluating for individual promotion and institutional visibility and competitiveness is the number and quality of academic papers published. Expectedly, majority of our respondents had published papers in academic journals in the past. Almost 10% of our respondents had never published. This finding is worrisome, and may affect their faith in the university system and the university ranking. A global report on Nigeria shows that the productivity per researcher is low (Mattia et al., 2019). A similar report was found in a Nigerian study (Ogbogu, 2009). Only 5.8% of respondents in our study had published 50 or more academic papers. It is important to note that the number of published articles is as important as the quality of the publication, because the “h-index”, “i10-index”, and the “citations” are partly derived from the number of publications/citations (Bornmann & Mutz, 2015). A study published in 2018 detailing topmost scholars and institutions by Google Scholar citation, had the following information: global ranking - Sigmund Freud of Vienna University (H-Index 280, citations 491861), and Nigerian ranking - Saviour Umoren of University of Uyo (H-Index 36, Citations 3736) (Omonijo et al.).

Publication rate in our study varied from none to 10 or more per year, with a greater number having 2-4 (161 = 36.8%), and 5-7 (132 = 30.1%) publications per year. A study published in year 2009 examined female academics research productivity in Nigeria's six geo-political zones, and found that 59.5% of females published only one paper per year, and 1.1% published three papers yearly (Ogbogu, 2009). There are other Nigerian studies with not too different research output (Okafor & Dike, 2010). Possible explanation for the relatively higher research productivity seen in our study could be the differences in time of evaluation (our study was done 13 years after), lack of sex discrimination in our study, and also non-segregation of research output into the different categories of academicians as the knowledge, opportunities, and motivation for publication may differ. However, a study in a private university in Nigeria reported that females ranked higher in journal article publications, while males topped the list in textbook publications (Okpe et al., 2013). There have been criticisms against undue emphasis on research productivity due to the dangers that could result from it: study results fractionation, re-using data in multiple publications, publishing results that are preliminary or incomplete, underemphasizing limitations, data fabrication, falsification and plagiarism (Bertamini & Munafò, 2012; Buela-Casal, 2014; Fanelli & Larivière, 2016; Hayer et al., 2013; Statzner & Resh, 2010; Ware & Munafò, 2015). Consequently, some governments / institutions limit the number of publications that could be in curriculum vitae for grants, or outrightly remove "productivity" category from ranking system (Fanelli & Larivière, 2016). However, in a low-income setting like ours where the conduct of research is being encouraged, research publication rate is a useful marker of some progress.

A statistically significant relationship existed in our study between lecturers who were involved in a collaboration and those who published academic papers in journals. This is in agreement with already existing information that scholar collaboration positively impacts on the number and quality of academic publications

(Franceschet & Costantini, 2010; Horta & Santos, 2016). Country collaboration between Germany and China was reported to have resulted in mutual benefits, with improvement in China's quality of publications (Zhou & Bornmann, 2015; Zhou & Lv, 2015). Although majority of respondents opined that they collaborated, were proficient in computer usage, and used some aids to academic publications, almost a third of them still experienced "late-hunting" for papers for promotion. A whole lot is needed for a successful research career, especially with modern tools in literature search, writing assistants (examples - ChatGPT, WordTune, and other artificial intelligence (AI) tools), grammar and paraphrasing, citations, illustrations, digital data (qualitative and quantitative), and productivity software. This may explain why respondents despite using different types of research aids in varying degrees, still had challenging issues bordering on lack of time for research, conceptualization of research idea, referencing, literature search, problems with research methodology, evaluation issues, organizational problems, difficulty with the art of writing and citing, and language insufficiency. Currently, different forms of AI writing tools have been developed to aid writing, although they have their merits, demerits, and ethical concerns (Al-Zahrani, 2024; Chirichela et al., 2024; Costa et al.; Dinçer, 2024; Khalifa & Albadawy, 2024; Lindberg & Domingues; Read et al., 2024; Stevkovska, 2025; Uno et al., 2024).

Other contributory factors as identified by respondents (specific impediments to academic writing) and asserted most were lack of funds for research, societal distractions, and poor knowledge of reference management software. Societal distractions in low-income countries could play a big role in negatively impacting on academicians by way of shifting their attention to economically rewarding ventures to attend to socioeconomic needs of "the family" (Rørstad & Aksnes, 2015). However, our study did not find any statistically significant relationship between any of these impediments and "ever published an article in journal". Rather, the factors that were associated with publishing academic papers were collaborating with others ($P < 0.001$),

academic rank ($P < 0.001$) and age ($P = 0.001$). The sex of the academician ($P = 0.441$), and marital status ($P = 0.101$) were however not associated with publishing in a journal. Our finding on sex of the academician is different from the observation in a private university where gender was a significant factor (Okpe et al., 2013). Gender differences in research performance between Italy vs Norway have also been observed (Abramo et al., 2021). The findings of other studies are also in support of our observations on academic rank and publication output (Abramo et al., 2011; Bentley & Kyvik, 2011).

Study Limitations

Some lecturers could not be reached in this study, and their opinion would probably have made some difference in this report. It is a questionnaire-based study and therefore limited by some recall bias characteristic of this type of study.

Conclusion

More than half of the academicians in Port Harcourt have published academic papers of different study designs, the most common being descriptive / observational studies. Although 5.8% of respondents had published 50 or more academic papers, 10% had never published any paper. Only 7.8% of the respondents had publication rate of 10 academic papers per year, 36.8% had 2-4 annual publications, and 30.1% 5-7. Despite their best efforts, 24.4% of respondents experienced "late-hunting" for papers for promotion. Challenges still exist among some academicians in terms of the different stages of academic paper publication – from idea conceptualization to journal publication. Foremost among impediments to academic writing were - lack of funds for research, societal distractions, and poor knowledge of reference management software.

Recommendations: We recommend that educational training institutions should intensify the drive in carrying out academic workshop for manuscript writing and reference management

software. Enrollment in other part-time courses that enhance academic writing (online or physical) would be useful. This could be in the form of departmentally arranged or individually arranged courses. Annual research grants should be provided for every fully employed university lecturer, different from the available tightly-regulated competitive grants from agencies.

Acknowledgement

We acknowledge the contributions of our field officers and some non-academic staff of the various institutions who painstakingly assisted in gathering data from the lecturers in the institutions amidst challenges.

Ethical Considerations

The approval of the Research Ethics Committee of the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital was obtained, and confidentiality of information was maintained in the process of data collection.

Conflict of Interest

None declared

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